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BREAST CANCER: RECENT REVIEW ON MICELLES AS NANO-CARRIERS FOR TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

Present review gives a brief explanation about Breast Cancer, its causes, factors that cause breast cancer, diagnosis, treatment, etc. A brief description of Cancer, and its types is also mentioned in this paper. Breast cancer is the most common female cancer in the world, Breast cancer incidence is rising all over the world, at different rates. Worldwide, breast cancer is ranked second in terms of incidence after lung cancer. This review emphasizes the use of nanocarriers which can be used as targeted drug delivery system. Brief information about micelles is mentioned in this review paper.

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer is one of the human severe diseases and causes increasing morbidity and mortality every year in the world. As a leading cancer type, breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed cancer among women worldwide. It is most common & in large percentage in Indian women than other countries. Tumor growth and systemic metastasis are highly dependent on angiogenesis. Angiogenesis promotes tumor growth by supplying nutrients and oxygen and removing waste products, meanwhile, facilitating tumor invasion and metastasis. Tumor less than 1 mm³ could receive necessary nutrients and oxygen by diffusion, however, tumor is unable to grow above 1 mm³ without neo vascularization. Angiogenesis is essential for tumor growth and metastasis, therefore antiangiogenesis has been proposed as a promising therapeutic strategy for clinical therapy of tumors. Anti angiogenic therapy aims to prevent the formation of new vessels around tumors and to frustrate the existing abnormal capillary network that supports the tumor.

In case of cancer treatment the major problem is Drug resistance which is basically associated with increased expression of MDR1 gene that encodes for drug efflux pump known as P-glycoprotein which leads to Multidrug resistance; various measures have been taken in order to overcome this drug resistance cancer.[1]

Cancer and cancer chemotherapy:

Cancer takes place by uncontrolled growth and spreading of abnormal cells. Cancer is very threatening disease and also a leading cause of death. It is of two types: benign and malignant. The cells of malignant tumors have the ability to attack neighboring tissues and organs, also the possibility of cancerous cells to rupture from the tumor and enter into the blood stream, thus spreading of the disease to other organs occur. This process of spreading is called metastasis. It is estimated that about 1.3 million new cases will be diagnosed and that more than half a million deaths will be caused by cancer in 2002, i.e., one in every four deaths.[2]

Causes of cancer:

Still the mechanisms of formation and spreading of cancer are not well understood; both external factors (e.g., tobacco smoking, chemicals, radiation, and infections) and internal factors (e.g., inherited metabolism mutations, hormones, and immune conditions) are supposed to be relevant. To initiate and promote carcinogenesis, these factors may act together or sequentially. From the beginning of cell mutation to the development of detectable cancer, it may take more than 10 years. There is a short of total cure for cancers. A worthy goal at the present is to develop treatments that produce remission and/or palliation. A cancer is said to be in remission when all clinical evidence of cancer has disappeared. [3]

Different types of cancer:

There are over 100 different types of cancer, affecting various parts of the body. Each type of cancer is unique with its own causes, symptoms, and methods of treatment, The most common types of cancer in the United States, based on frequency of diagnosis are:

1. Breast Cancer
2. Bladder Cancer
3. Brain Cancer
4. Colon Cancer
5. Endometrial Cancer
6. Kidney Cancer (Renal Cell)
7. Leukaemia
8. Cervical Cancer
9. Lung Cancer
10. Melanoma
11. Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma
12. Pancreatic Cancer
13. Prostate Cancer
14. Thyroid Cancer

Breast Cancers-

Breast cancer (BC) is the most common malignancy in women. Breast cancer is a malignant tumor (a collection of cancer cells) arising from the cells of the breast. Breast cancer is the most common female cancer worldwide representing nearly a quarter (23%) of all cancers in women. With growing proportions from developing countries the global burden of breast cancer is expected to cross 2 million by the year 2030. Even though age-standardised incidence rates in India are inferior than in the United Kingdom (UK) (25.8 versus 95 per 100,000), mortality rates are nearly as high (12.7 versus 17.1 per 100,000, respectively) as those of the UK. Breast cancer frequency rates within India display a 3–4-fold dissimilarity across the country, with the highest rates experiential in the Northeast and in major metropolitan cities such as Mumbai and New Delhi.

The increase in global burden of breast cancer, especially in developing countries undergoing rapid socio-economic changes, has been intricately woven with reproductive, dietary, and hormonal risk factors. Incidence has been rising in most regions of the world, but there are huge inequalities between rich and poor countries. Incidence rates remain maximum in more developed regions, but mortality is relatively much higher in less developed countries due to a lack of early detection and access to treatment facilities. An abnormal and uncontrolled growth of cells in breast are termed as breast cancer.

There are three major subtypes of Breast cancer based on the presence or absence of molecular markers for estrogens or progesterone receptors and human epidermal growth factor 2 (*ERBB2*; formerly *HER2*): hormone receptor positive/*ERBB2* negative (70% of patients), *ERBB2* positive (15%-20%), and triple-negative (tumours lacking all 3 standard molecular markers; 15%). [4]

At the time of diagnosis it was observed that more than 90% of breast cancers are not metastatic. Therapeutic goals are tumor eradication and preventing recurrence for people presenting without metastatic disease. Triple-negative breast cancer is more likely to recur than the other 2 subtypes, with 85% 5-year breast cancer-specific survival for stage I triple-negative tumours vs. 94% to 99% for hormone receptor positive and *ERBB2* positive. Systemic therapy for non metastatic breast cancer is determined by subtype: a minority receive chemotherapy and patients with hormone receptor-positive tumours receive endocrine therapy, and as well; patients with *ERBB2*-positive tumours receive *ERBB2*-targeted antibody or small-molecule inhibitor therapy combined with chemotherapy; and patients with triple-negative tumours receive chemotherapy only.

With consideration of postoperative radiation if lumpectomy is performed, Local therapy for all patients with non metastatic breast cancer consists of surgical resection. Progressively more, some systemic therapy is delivered before surgery. Tailoring postoperative treatment based on preoperative treatment response is under investigation. The breast cancer which is metastatic is treated according to subtype, with goals of prolonging life and palliating symptoms. Median overall survival for metastatic triple-negative breast cancer is approximately 1 year vs approximately 5 years for the other 2 subtypes.[5]

Sign & Symptoms of breast cancer

There are many different signs and symptoms of breast cancer. Common breast cancer signs and symptoms include a lump or swelling in the breast, upper chest or armpit. You might feel the lump, but not see it. The Changes in the size or shape of the breast are observed. A change in skin texture i.e. puckering or dimpling of the skin is also observed also a change in the colour of the breast - the breast may look red or inflamed. Rash, crusting or changes to the nipple is observed.

Risk factors for breast cancer:

The exact cause of breast cancer is not fully known, but we know that the risk of breast cancer increases as the age increases. Various risk factors for breast cancer include a personal or family history of breast cancer and the occurrence of certain benign conditions in the breast. People who have inherited certain genetic mutations (*BRCA1*, *BRCA2*) are also at increased risk of getting breast cancer and other cancers. The chances of breast cancer increase as one gets older. The risk of breast cancer is higher among women who have relatives with the disease. The major risk of breast cancer is when a close relative suffers with the disease (sister, mother, and daughter). The risk of cancer in the other breast or the chance of an additional cancer in the original breast when there is diagnosis in one breast. Women diagnosed with certain non-cancerous breast conditions have an increased risk of breast cancer. These include a typical hyperplasia, a condition in which there is abnormal proliferation of breast cells but no cancer has developed. Women who started their menstrual cycle at a younger age (before 12) or went through menopause later (after 55) have a slightly increased risk. Women with dense breast tissue (as documented by mammogram) have a higher risk of breast cancer. White women have a higher risk of developing breast cancer, but African-American women tend to have more tumors that are aggressive when they do develop breast cancer. Exposure to previous chest radiation or use of diethylstilbestrol increases the risk of breast cancer. Having no children or the first child after age 30 increases the risk of breast cancer. Breastfeeding for one and a half to two years might slightly lower the risk of breast cancer. Being overweight or obese increases the risk of breast cancer both in pre- and postmenopausal women but at different rates. Use of oral contraceptives in the last 10 years increases the risk of breast cancer slightly. Using combined hormone therapy after menopause increases the risk of breast cancer. Alcohol consumption increases the risk of breast cancer, and this seems to be proportional to the amount of alcohol used. A recent meta-analysis reviewing the research on alcohol use and breast cancer concluded that all levels of alcohol use are associated with an increased risk for breast cancer. This includes even light drinking. Exercise seems to lower the risk of breast cancer. Genetic risk factors are the most common causes are mutations in the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes (breast cancer and ovarian cancer genes). Inheriting a mutated gene from a parent means that one has a significantly higher risk of developing breast cancer.[6]

Types of breast cancer

There are many types of breast cancer. Some are more common than others, and there are also combinations of cancers. Some of the most common types of cancer are as follows:

Ductal carcinoma in situ

The most common type of non-invasive breast cancer is ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS). This early-stage breast cancer has not spread and therefore usually has a very high cure rate.

Invasive ductal carcinoma

This cancer starts in the milk ducts of the breast and grows into other parts of the surrounding tissue. It is the most common form of breast cancer. About 80% of invasive breast cancers are invasive ductal carcinoma.

Invasive lobular carcinoma

This breast cancer starts in the milk-producing glands of the breast. Approximately 10% of invasive breast cancers are invasive lobular carcinoma.

The remainder of breast cancers are much less common and include the following:

1. **Mucinous carcinoma** :This is formed from mucus-producing cancer cells. Mixed tumors contain a variety of cell types.
2. **Medullary carcinoma** :This is an infiltrating breast cancer that presents with well-defined boundaries between the cancerous and noncancerous tissue.
3. **Inflammatory breast cancer**: This cancer makes the skin of the breast appear red and feel warm (giving it the appearance of an infection). These changes are due to the blockage of lymph vessels by cancer cells.
4. **Triple-negative breast cancers**: This is a subtype of invasive cancer with cells that lack estrogen and progesterone receptors and have no excess of a specific protein (HER2) on their surface. It tends to appear more often in younger women and African-American women.
5. **Paget's disease of the nipple**: This cancer starts in the ducts of the breast and spreads to the nipple and the area surrounding the nipple. It usually presents with crusting and redness around the nipple.
6. **Adenoid cystic carcinoma**: These cancers have both glandular and cystic features. They tend not to spread aggressively and have a good prognosis.
7. **Lobular carcinoma in situ**: This is not a cancer but an area of abnormal cell growth. This pre-cancer can increase the risk of invasive breast cancer later in life.

The following are other uncommon types of breast cancer:

- Papillary carcinoma
- Phyllodes tumor
- Angiosarcoma
- Tubular carcinoma

Drugs commonly used to treat Lungs cancer:

While a very large number of agents targeting various molecular pathways are being developed and tested, the main classes and agents that are now being used in lung cancer treatment include:

Anthracyclines

- ✓ Doxorubicin
- ✓ Pegylated liposomal doxorubicin
- ✓ Epirubicin

Taxanes

- ✓ Paclitaxel (Taxol)
- ✓ Docetaxel (Taxotere)
- ✓ Albumin-bound Paclitaxel(Abraxane)

Platinum agents

- ✓ Cisplatin
- ✓ Carboplatin

Vinorelbine(Navelbine)**Capecitabine(Xeloda)****Gemcitabine(Gemzar)****Eribulin(Halaven)****Use of phytochemical for the treatment of breast cancer**

In locally advanced breast cancer, 50% of the cases are observed with resistance to radiotherapy due to hypoxic tumor microenvironment. A plethora of recent research has been focused on exploiting the pharmacologically safe, bioactive phytochemical as breast cancer preventive and therapeutic agents. Phytochemicals are among the most promising chemo preventive treatment options for the management of cancer. The ideal characteristics that chemo preventive/therapeutic agents should possess include restoration of normal growth control to preneoplastic or malignant cells by modulating aberrant signaling pathways and/or inducing apoptosis; and targeting the multiple biochemical and physiological pathways of tumor development.

A large number of phytoconstituents have been shown to kill breast tumor cells and prevent the occurrence or suppress the growth of mammary tumours in various animal models via modulation of proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, oxidative stress, inflammation, angiogenesis and several cell signaling pathways implicated in the initiation, promotion and progression of breast cancer. Consumption of various dietary agents, including citrus fruits, soy, green tea or carotenoids has been associated with a reduced breast cancer risk. Several clinical intervention trials evaluated the efficacy of various natural products, including Phytochemicals and dietary supplements, in breast cancer prevention and treatment.

A standard breast cancer treatment protocol involves suppression of estrogen production/effect .The general strategies to inhibit estrogen action are to block ER binding to its specific ligand or to disrupt estrogen production by altering the aromatase gene expression or enzyme activities.

ER antagonists can block estrogenic actions and aromatase inhibitors suppress estrogen production. Many antiestrogen-treated tumours retain their ER expression during recurrence, but signaling through the ER pathway is altered in these resistant tumours. Thus, it is clear that targeting this pathway using Phytochemicals, may affect the development of both primary and secondary cancers.

Phytoestrogens are appeared to mitigate estrogenic signaling in the presence of both ER subtypes but, in late-stage cancer cells lacking ER β , these Phytochemicals contributed to a tumor-promoting transcriptional signature. A biphasic activity of Phytoestrogens has been reported during cancer development in estrogen-sensitive tissues and the beneficial effects of Phytoestrogens depend on the timing of exposure. Initially, Phytoestrogens are able to slow down cell growth by activating ER β , thereby generating an ant proliferative expression signature. Due to the genetic instability of malignant cells, however, the expression of ER β may be abrogated by gene deletion or promoter methylation. In such late-stage cancer cells, Phytoestrogens, in conjunction with other estrogenic chemicals, induce a transcriptional profile that promotes the proliferation of those clones that exhibit high amounts of ER α but little ER β . In light of these considerations, the potentially beneficial effect of Phytoestrogens should be re-evaluated; particularly in relation to risk groups that are susceptible to the development of ER α -positive tumours arising from steroid hormone-dependent tissues.[7]

Nanotechnology

Nanotechnology, a term derived from the Greek word 'Nano' meaning dwarf, applies the principles of engineering, electronics, physical and material science and manufacturing at a molecular or submicron level. The development of effective drug delivery systems that can transport and deliver a drug precisely and safely to its site of action is becoming a highly important research area for pharmaceutical researchers. Indeed, a great number of new delivery technologies surface each year and nearly every part of the body has been studied as a potential route for administering both classical and novel medicines [8]. Conventional drug delivery system achieves as well as maintains the drug concentration within the therapeutically effective range needed for treatment only when taken several times a day. This results in a significant fluctuation in drug level. Therefore it led to the development of new controlled drug delivery system that could revolutionize method of medication and provide a number of therapeutic benefits.[9].The input of today's nanotechnology is that it allows real progress to achieve temporal and spatial site-specific delivery. The market of nanotechnology and drug delivery systems based on this technology will be widely touched by the pharmaceutical industry. In recent years, the number of patents and products in this field is increasing significantly.[10]

Colloidal drug delivery system

Targeted delivery of drug molecules to organs or special sites is one of the most challenging research areas in pharmaceutical sciences. By developing colloidal delivery systems such as liposomes, micelles and nanoparticles a new frontier was opened for improving drug delivery. Nanoparticles can be administered via different routes of administration such as parenteral, oral, intraocular, transdermal or pulmonary inhalation. This carrier system should have no toxicity (acute and chronic), have a sufficient drug loading capacity and the possibility of drug targeting and controlled release characteristics. It should also provide chemical and physical stability for the incorporated drug. The feasibility of production scaling up with reasonable overall costs should be available.[11],[12],[13].

Carrier systems that facilitate the intestine uptake of new molecules are of major interest in the drug delivery area. Drug delivery systems that provide a route of administration that does not involve injection can improve the patient compliance and expand the market for existing, injectable drugs. The factors which are important for the oral efficiency of a vehicle system are small particle size, appropriate surface property, and mucoadhesive and targeting moieties, stability, as well as dose are the major factors imparting the efficiency of oral uptake.[14]

Need of nanometric colloidal carriers

Colloidal systems, particularly those in the nanosized range, have been increasingly investigated in the last years because they can fulfill the requirements mentioned above.[15],[16],[17] Nanosized carriers are treated as hopeful means to increase the solubility and therefore the bioavailability of poorly water-soluble active ingredients belonging to the classes II and IV in the biopharmaceutical classification system (BCS) when delivery of these drugs by oral route is concerned and also they provide targeted delivery of a drug into particular organ or tissue and for some specific need or demand.

Fig- 1: Dimension of nanotechnology.

Nanocarriers in Chemotherapy-

A nanocarrier is nano material being used as a transport module for another substance, such as a drug. Commonly used nano carriers include micelles, liposomes etc. Nanocarriers are currently being studied for their use in drug delivery and their unique characteristics to demonstrate potential use in chemotherapy [18], [19]. Conventional therapeutic agents are distributed non-specifically in body, affecting both target and normal cells. This phenomenon has reduced the efficient dose of the drugs reaching the target cells, then caused by suboptimal results due to excessive toxicity.

A very promising approach to overcome systemic toxicity is the application of drug-loaded nanosized drug carriers, such as liposomes, polymeric nanoparticles, dendrimers and micelles [20]. Nanocarriers were able to diminish toxicity of the therapeutic agents in neighbour cells and have selectively augmented the amount of drugs accumulated within target cells.[24] Therefore Nanocarriers are being employed largely these days for treating Cancers as compared to that of Conventional Therapy. Apart from it, the first rationale to use nanomedicine for cancer therapy is the preferential delivery of nano-vectorized drugs to solid tumors due to the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect [21].

Nanocarriers may deliver a relatively high drug load, which may overwhelm drug efflux mechanisms of cancer cells, thereby enhancing the anticancer effect of the drug. Furthermore, drug-loaded nanoparticles may accumulate more at the tumor site, which is secondary to the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect[12,13]. Commonly used nanocarrier platforms include liposomes, polymeric micelles, dendrimers, and mesoporous silica particles [22].

Micelles - A Nanocarrier for Cancer Treatment

Fig-9: Structure of Polymeric Micelle.

Micelles are spherical nanoparticles with a core-shell structure having hydrophobic cores and hydrophilic shells; hydrophobic micelle cores serve for encapsulation of lipophilic drugs. Micelle formation is thermodynamically driven; micelles are formed by self-assembly of individual molecules (unimers) of amphiphilic block copolymer.[23]. A typical micelle in aqueous solution forms an aggregate with the hydrophilic head regions in contact with surrounding solvent, sequestering the hydrophobic single tail regions in the micelle centre. The major driving force behind self-association of amphiphilic molecules is the decrease of free energy of the system.

The decrease in free energy is a result of removal of hydrophobic fragments from the aqueous surroundings with the formation of a micelle core stabilized with hydrophilic fragments exposed into water.[28]. Micelles are capable of solubilising the hydrophobic drugs even at higher concentrations. At low concentrations in an aqueous medium, the amphiphiles exist as monomers in true solution, but when the concentration increases, aggregation and self-assembly take place within a narrow concentration window, and micelles are formed. The concentration at which micelles are formed is referred to as the critical micelle concentration (CMC).

It has been reported that the co-delivery of combined anti-cancer drugs to tumor cells using nanocarriers is a hopeful strategy for treating MDR [6-7]. Various nanocarriers have been investigated, including lipid nanoparticles, polymeric nanoparticles, polymeric micelles,

liposomes, and dendrimers, etc.. Among them, self-assembly polymeric micelles are very attractive for co-delivery of multiple anticancer agents. This is because i) the hydrophobic core could allow for loading hydrophobic drug compounds such as anticancer drugs; ii) the outer hydrophilic shell could prolong circulation time; and iii) they could provide sustained drug release profiles [24].

Recently, different classical and successful nanotherapeutics used to transport anticancer drugs into tumors have been fabricated and applied in order to improve the anticancer effect of chemotherapeutic drugs, the most prominent among which include polymeric nanocarriers such as liposomes, supramolecular derivatives and ultradeformable vesicles. As one of the promising nanoparticulate approaches, the mixed micelle carriers formed by triblock copolymers for delivery of anticancer drugs have been basically exploited in various clinical applications for the merits of smaller size, self-assembling ability, solubilisation and protection against unstable drugs.

Fig-10: Schematic representation of various techniques for the preparation of polymer nanoparticles.[25].

Types of Micelles-

1) Depending upon the nature of core shell-

- Normal Phase Micelle – Where the core layer is hydrophobic in nature in which the drug is being incorporated, and this layer is surrounded by hydrophilic layer.
- Reverse Phase Micelle – Here the core layer is hydrophilic in nature surrounded by a external hydrophobic layer.

2) Depending upon the nature of the micelles and the intended action to be produced-

- Stimuli-Sensitivity
- Acid-Sensitive Polymeric Micelles
- Thermo-sensitive Polymeric Micelles

Amphiphilic Block Co-polymers-

An Amphiphile is a term describing a chemical compound possessing both hydrophilic and lipophilic properties. The most important feature of this Amphiphilic Block Co-Polymers is its ability to self-assemble in solution giving rise to a plethora of resulting morphologies including spherical micelles, cylindrical micelles, lamellae and vesicles and bicontinuous structures, among others. These Polymers are being Synthesized by various polymerisation methods, which facilitate the preparation of block copolymers with well-defined compositions, molecular weights, and elaborate architectures. Amphiphilic copolymers provide better kinetic and thermodynamic stability than conventional surfactant. The hydrophobic core of micelles can solubilize poorly soluble drugs and partly protect the drug from the aqueous environment.[26].

Table 2: Types of Amphiphilic co-polymers used for Micelle Preparation[27].

Structure of Micelle-forming Co-polymers	
Type of micelle forming copolymers	Representation of structure
Block copolymers	di-block AAAAAAABBBBBB
	Tri-block AAAABBBBBAAAA
	AAAAAABBBBBAAAA
Graft copolymers	AAAAAAAAAAAAA
	B B
	B B B

Table 3: Various types of amphiphilic Block Co-polymers.

Linear Block Copolymer	Graft Copolymers
Dendritic Polymers	Starlike Polymers
Cyclic Polymers	

Linear amphiphilic block co-polymers

Linear amphiphilic block copolymers which are generally defined as macromolecules consisting of two or more chemically distinct and frequently immiscible blocks linked together by covalent bonds [Example TPGS]. This immiscibility results in their self assembly in solutions of a selective solvent of one of the blocks. In particular, when a block copolymer is dissolved in a liquid that is a thermodynamically good solvent for one block and at the same time a precipitant for the other, the copolymer chains associate reversibly thus forming micellar aggregates of nanoscopic dimensions and of various shapes, similar to those obtained from low molecular weight surfactants. The resulting micelles consist of a more or less swollen core of the insoluble blocks surrounded by a flexible corona of the soluble blocks.

Various Factors affecting the process of micelle formation-

- 1) Size of the hydrophobic domain in the amphiphilic molecule
- 2) Concentration of amphiphiles
- 3) Temperature being set
- 4) Solvent being used

Ideal Properties of Polymeric Micelles-

1. They should be nano sized structures having size ranges from 10-100nm.
2. They should be small enough in size (~10-200 nm) to effectively penetrate into tissue.
3. They should be unrecognizable by the mononuclear phagocyte system (MPS) for a sufficient time to allow accumulation in target tissue.
4. They should be eliminated from the organism either after degradation or dissolution.
5. They should locate and interact with the target cells.
6. They should have considerable stability.
7. They should be responsible for the improvement of pharmacokinetic (PK) profile of the encapsulated drug.
8. They should possess high loading capacity.

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REFERENCES

1. Feng S, Chien, S. Chemotherapeutic engineering: Application and further development of chemical engineering principles for chemotherapy of cancer and other diseases. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 2003; 58:4087.
2. Sinha Dona, Sarkar Nivedita, Biswas Jaydip, Bishayee Anupam. Resveratrol for breast cancer prevention and therapy. Preclinical evidence and molecular mechanisms. *Seminars in Cancer Biology.* 2015:4512.
3. Eric P, Adrienne G, Waks MD and Winer MD. Breast Cancer Treatment: A Review. *JAMA.* 2019;321(3):288.
4. Zohre Momenimovahed, Hamid Salehiniya, Epidemiological characteristics of and risk factors for breast cancer in the world. *Breast Cancer - Targets and Therapy.* 2019;11:151.
5. Siddiqui JA, Singh A, Chagtoo M, Singh N, Godbole MM, Chakravarti B. Phytochemicals for breast cancer therapy: current status and future implications. 2015; 15(2):116-35.
6. Patel S, Nanda R, Sahoo S. Nanotechnology in Healthcare: Applications and Challenges. *Med chem.* 2015;5:528.
7. Chien Y. W. Novel drug delivery system. New York: Marcel Dekker Inc. 1992;50(2).
8. Pathak Y and Thassu D. Recent Developments in Nanoparticulate Drug Delivery Systems. *Drug Delivery Nanoparticles Formulation and Characterization.* 2009: 1-15.
9. Barratt G. Therapeutic applications of colloidal drug carriers. *Pharm. Sci. Tech. Today.* 2000;3 (5): 163.
10. Mehnert W and Mader K. Solid lipid nanoparticles Production, characterization and applications. *Adv. Drug Delivery.* 2001;47: 165.
11. Mainardes R and Silva L. Drug delivery systems: past, present and future. *Curr. Drug Targets.* 2004; 5 (5): 449.
12. Zarif L. Cochleates as Nanoparticulate Drug Carriers. *Nanoparticulates as drug carriers.* 2006 : 349.
13. Md Asif Iqbal, Shadab Md, Jasjeet Kaur Sahni, Sanjula Baboota, Shweta Dang & Javed Ali. Nanostructured lipid carriers system: Recent advances in drug delivery. *Journal of Drug Targeting.* 2012;20(10),813.
14. Han F, Li S, Yin R., Liu H and Xu L. Effect of surfactants on the formation and characterization of a new type of colloidal drug delivery system : Nanostructured lipid carriers. *Colloids Surf. A: Physicochem. Eng. Aspects.* 2008;315: 210–216
15. Vyas, S. P. and Khar, R. K. Targeted & Controlled Drug Delivery. Novel Carrier Systems. CBS Publisher & Distributor. New Delhi. 2004: 249.
16. Kumari P, Ghosh B and Biswas S. Nanocarriers for cancer-targeted drug delivery. *Journal of drug targeting.* 2016;24(3):179.
17. Fakhar ud Din, Waqar Aman, Izhar Ullah, Omer Salman Qureshi, Omer Mustapha, Shumaila Shafique, Alam Zeb. Effective use of nanocarriers as drug delivery systems for the treatment of selected tumors. *Int J Nanomedicine.* 2017; 12: 7291–7309
18. Orlemans C, Bult W, Bos M, Storm G, Nijsen J.F.W and Hennink W.E. Polymeric micelles in anticancer therapy: targeting, imaging and triggered release. *Pharmaceutical research.* 2010; 27(12):2569.
19. Hadi Khodabandehloo, Hamid Zahednasab, Asghar Ashrafi Hafez. *Iran J Cancer Prev.* 2016; 9(2):3966

20. Emami J, Rezazadeh M, Hasanzadeh F, Sad eghi H, Mostafavi A, Minaiyan M, Rostami M and Davies N. Development and in vitro/in vivo evaluation of a novel targeted polymeric micelle for delivery of paclitaxel. International journal of biological macromolecules.2015;80:29.
21. Chen-Yang Zhao , Rui Cheng , Zhe Yang and Zhong-Min Tian. Nanotechnology for Cancer Therapy Based on Chemotherapy.Molecules.2018;23:826.
22. Gupta R, Shea J, Scaife C, Shurlygina A and Rapoport N. Polymeric micelles and nanoemulsions as drug carriers: Therapeutic efficacy, toxicity, and drug resistance. Journal of Controlled Release.2015; 212: 70.
23. Mourya V.K, Inamdar N, Nawale R.B and Kulthe S.S. Polymeric micelles: general considerations and their applications. Ind. J. Pharm. Edu. Res.2011; 45; 128.
24. Khan DR. The use of Nanocarriers for Drug Delivery in Cancer Therapy. J Cancer Sci Ther.2010; 2: 058
25. Gao Y, Li L.B and Zhai G. Preparation and characterization of Pluronic/TPGS mixed micelles for solubilization of camptothecin. Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces.2008;64(2): 194.
26. Neophytou C.M. and Constantinou A.I. Drug delivery innovations for enhancing the anticancer potential of Vitamin E isoforms and their derivatives. BioMed research international.2015:1220
27. Alexandridis P. Amphiphilic copolymers and their applications. Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science.1996;1(4): 490.

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